

**DEVELOPING THE EVALUATION MODEL
THROUGH LEARNING MANAGEMENT INTEGRATING UNIFIED
INSTRUCTIONS OF THE BASIC EDUCATIONAL TEACHERS
UNDER OFFICE OF THE BASIC EDUCATION COMMISSION (OBEC)**

Ronnachai Srisuthunyavong¹ⁱ,

Piyatida Punya²,

Nuttachai Juntachum³

^{1,2,3}Research and Evaluation Program, Faculty of Education
Rajabhat Maha Sarakham University, Maha Sarakham, Thailand, 44000

Abstract:

The aim of this research study was to develop the evaluation model (EM) through learning management integrating unified instructions (LMIUI) of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC) with the research and development process. To have integrated with the texts, documents, reports, research articles, and a database of three professional education experts was interviewed. The draft evaluation form to verify the suitability and feasibility of this evaluating draft form with nine qualified experts using a technique based on a specialized symposium (Connoisseurship). The EM model estimates to trial in 13 basic schools under the Roi-Et Primary Educational Service Area Office 1. The EM model was assessed with the feasibility of appropriate dimensions for accuracy and usefulness by the board of evaluators was involved in determining the concurrent validity forms of assessment and evaluation form that the dimensions of the possibility of reasonable involved in the trial EM form. The results of this research have found that: the factors of the EM model through the LMIMU should contain four components. The first component includes the preparation teaching has six indicator components, the second on the learning process has three components above 10 indicate, the third element of the learning media has four indicators, and the fourth components on the measurement and evaluation of learning contained 10 indicate were developed. In terms of the evaluation of the EM model, the components include the rationale for the assessment,

the goal of the assessment, the evaluation focused on components and indicators. The process and method of evaluation consists of four phases: preparatory assessment, the evaluation process and the conclusion of the assessment report, evaluation criteria was an absolute criterion by fixing a percentage of the guide contains the descriptions and application quality, evaluator sources, the evaluating instrument, collected data, data analysis, and the evaluation summary report were appropriate and the possibility as high level. The concurrent validity of the LMIUI instructional teachers, it has found that the overall of training academic teachers rating was higher than the teachers who had not been trained that evidence of statistical significance at 0.01 levels, differently. The perceptions for involving evaluation groups in the overall trial of the EM model were individual components at a high level. The overall results of the EM model with the LMIMI instruction indicated the possibility of reasonable accuracy and usefulness at a high level, significantly.

Keywords: development, the evaluation model, learning management, integrating unified instructions

1. Introduction

The Education Act BE 2542, as amended (No. 2) Act BE 2545, the Article 4 mentions; education is a learning process, to the growth of individuals and society, the knowledge transfer training workshops cultural heritage and invention, the academic progress for creating knowledge is arising from the social environment of learning and other factors contribute to individual learning continues throughout life. The Article 6 mentions; the principles of education must be to develop Thai people, as well as a complete human body, mind, intellect, knowledge, ethics and culture to life can co-exist happily with others. The Article 22 mentions; defines the guidelines for the management of education that it must be based on the principle that all learners are able to learn and develop themselves. It is considered the most important lessons that teachers and education managers must change the role of a guide. The transfer of knowledge to promote and assist learners in acquiring knowledge from the media and learning resources, and provide accurate information to learners to put them to use their knowledge creatively (Office for Standards and Quality Assessment BE 2010: 2-5).

Learning management is a critical process in the course curriculum into practice with the Core Basic Education Act BE 2551 is, of course, a learning standard that indicators of learner performance. The desirable characteristics are important destinations for the development of children and youth. The lesson to be learned that according to the learning standards and indicators of their performance and desirable

characteristics as defined in the core curriculum of the Basic Education Act BE 2551. The principle that learning is most important that it believes that everyone has the ability to learn and develop themselves. The benefit to the learners' process of their learning to encourage them for developing their full potential and natural. Regardless of the differences between individuals and brain development both stressed the importance of learning, knowledge, and integrity. Teachers need to select the learning process were designed to comply with the potential and contextual learning of the learners. To determine the role of the teacher and the learner for using a variety of learning materials and the design and evaluation to develop the learners to meet learning standards in eight subject groups are contributed to the development of competencies of the learners and desirable's behaviors (The Academic and Educational Standards Office. 2009: 1)

The Core Curriculum for Basic Education Act BE 2551 specified that in learning process will require a rich learning. As a tool to develop the learners into the program goals. The teacher must know and understand the concept to their learning management and the effects on the learners who are learning to facilitate the development of their coursework to their integrated learning process. The learning content management, learning a coherent set of learning activities to help the learners knowledge, understanding in a way that is holistic and knowledge, understanding application in daily life, and integrating learning management. There are many variations depending on suitability and the suitability of the learners toward their and learning. (Academic and educational standards. 2009: 12)

The process of the unit integrated into practice in the classroom is bought with learning management to help learners who meet and set a course to make learning effectively in developing learners. Teachers must have a deep understanding of the principles and concepts related to the focus on learning core curriculum of Basic Education Act BE 2551, which is of course a learning standards and indicators, performance of learners, and desirable as a goal of developing the learners, the integration of learning management, the learning process in relation to the subject, and/or between a group learning. The goal is to improve the quality of learning in each group learning areas such as; knowledge, ideas, skills/experience, and the performance of learners to improve the desirable characteristics as a whole to be enlightened know what studies can be applied in real life. Teachers need to learn a variety of processes, applied learning with the technical or management know-appropriate learning standards and indicators in content and potential of the learners. Focusing on giving the learners study and learn on their own to share with friends in the group to help the learners achieve learning goals, the unit is so integrated learning management must take into learners' center, to provide a consistent experience to take them into account the differences between individuals awareness of values and ethics that must be pretty

good. Learners ought to develop the critical 21st skills, including life and career skills, learning and innovation skills to their information, media and technology skills of their learning to adapt to the ASEAN (Asian Community).

In terms of the developing learners as a paradigm to learn consists of five steps in the development of the group: learning to question, learning to seek information, learning to build knowledge, learning to communicate, and learning to serve society. Classroom learning environments should be encouraged learning to think that are right to their age-appropriate. The learners worked in groups with their interactions to their cognitive self and their exchange of learning each other in order to have their learning. In addition, the event learning is the key to helping learners achieve the program goals and truly integration achievements. Assigning learning activities that help develop learners should look like this: to relate closely linked to learning standards and metrics is the goal of learning, to help build knowledge and skills. To develop the learners into learning standards set, to encourage the learners to participate in learning, to encourage the learners to develop thinking skills for taking into account the differences between individuals of the learners, to learn with self-knowledge and activities that allow them to build a portfolio or workload can be assessed. (The Academic and Educational Standards, 2013: 15-16).

Historical background of the integration learning was a focus of many religious institutions of higher education. The broad concept encompasses the idea that the Christian worldview, faith, and practices of the learner should be deeply connected to the learning experience. That said, different educators build their own visions of education onto the concept, what some call conceptions of faith-learning integration (Dockery, 2000). The integration learning management is managed by a teacher who must use assessment and evaluation methods, the reflective quality of the learner learning standards and indicators of their moral and conducted concurrently in the process of learning. In order to collect the data that needs to measure and evaluate the learners on every side on the two basic principles, such as; the assessment is to develop, to determine learner outcomes, to improve the quality of learning will achieve the learners. Learners need to be developed and evaluated learning to achieve the learning standards and indicators. The reflecting the performance of learners and their desirable is the goal of the development of the learners that the basic principle of such assessments. Assessment to develop learners (Formative Evaluation) to monitor the learning progress of students to bring development to meet learning standards and indicators can also be used as a developmental learning by teachers. This should be done in parallel with the regular curriculum, therefore, regularly and use a variety of assessment methods. The teachers are able to measure and evaluate. Learning based on indicators in the subject area of their responsibility for the learning activities listed to choose and evaluate appropriate and consistent with the work/tasks. The requiring

learners to follow learning activities to save evaluation and assessment to improve students' individual potential in group or a classroom by learning standards and indicators specified of an evaluation should use quality learning instruments.

Integration of unit learning can be implemented as the first two cases, the evaluation unit to integrate all learning and covers all standard learning and indicators, and the second measurement and evaluation unit to integrate some of the issues, some learning standards and indicators. The Bureau of Standards Education (2013) establish guidelines to improve the quality of teaching and learning, and preparing students to enter the world of the 21st century and assigned the Office of the Basic Education. Guidelines learning management integration, unified management focus on planning activities for mutual learning of teachers in the same class as a system for guiding of teachers and staff involved in its implementation in order to reduce the content, redundancy, and workload of teachers, the burden of homework of course. The maintaining the quality in terms of knowledge and the time to do activities outside the classroom to gain more experience on increase. The process is aimed at teachers, especially teachers in the same grade level to plan together to analyze the course, determining the orientation of the learning process, measurement and evaluation to determine the quality of the students have covered all the issues. As well as monitoring and providing workload and work properly on a daily basis this marks a change management learning that will take place concretely.

In fact, human life is integrated. Life is not fragmented; the education of the study is modular fragmentation, which is clearly visible in the school system. Both primary and secondary students who are learning the course and there is no relationship between study as a result, the students have to memorize the contents and learn different skills dissociation can't link what they learn in various subjects that make or do things modular throughout students to think critically enough thought. The idea of synthetic always associate the knowledge that have learned is not able to apply the knowledge in various disciplines to integrate in order to have a complete knowledge of the work was used of living. Learning is not related to the reality of life and learners confuse knowledge with students from the school of life. The issue for the management of basic education quality for students can develop and achieve program goals and be able to solve the problem of education as a separate subject has had a policy of only providing education curriculum integrating unified. (The Office of Academic and Educational Standards. 2013: 1)

The learning management integrating unified instruction is a important learning process to deal with the links courses to the curriculum, measurement and evaluation comprehensive, knowledge, ideas, skills and experience with a variety of meanings relationships and a holistic the enlightened know that correspond to the realities of life and to reform education in the second decade (BE 2552-2561), whose goal is to solve the

problems arising from the use of the core curriculum studies for the basic edition is used every year that including the duplication of the content taught separately and the burden of redundant tasks, such as; homework and take classes to suit the development of learners at different ages, a burden to the students who are as well as opening a new dimension of learning aimed at developing students to know never stop on their learning. The analysis process and self-knowledge that can be applied to achieve a lasting learning. The skills required in the world in the 21st century, where the above principles is important to solve the problem of overlapping learning content of each subject. It complements the focus on improving the quality of the students to clear up of their reduced workload, such as homework and the opportunity to do more learning outside the classroom that it right to development by age (The Office of Academic and Educational Standards. 2013: 1).

According to the Education Act BE 2542, as mentioned in the introduction and currently there was no concept, clear guidelines on the dimensions of the assessment, learning management, integrating unified. The teacher said it was not found to have some form of assessment, learning management integration, a full range of teachers, which is developing guides to assess learning integration services. The teachers who will bring benefits the value in the center of the concept and the formal evaluation of learning management, integrated unified was evaluated. Teachers used to describe the nature of the assessment, learning management integration, a full range of teachers and guidelines for evaluating the appropriate context in which to study. The expansion and development of knowledge about assessment, learning management, integrated unified in such cases. If the assessment is a process to gather and use the information to improve decision-making in education. Research to obtain a form to assess learning management integration, a full range of teachers. It is used as a educational instrument of the national education has done, in addition to the knowledge of the science of assessment, all the reasons mentioned as above is the motive for the researchers to develop guidelines to assess the developing the evaluation model through learning management integrating unified instructions of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC). The information from the EM to the development process and improve learning management integration, a full range of teachers in the basic education under the Office of Basic Education have been changed of the quality even further.

2. Methodology

Learning Management is our fully-integrated learning management system that offers teachers and students a powerful solution that enhances blended learning programs, flipped classroom instruction, and 1:1 device programs. Teachers and students can

learn and collaborate in a familiar social environment; seamless integration brings the grade book, report card, and the LMS together, no need for a clunky sync process or dual entry of grades and data across multiple platforms, and organizes class content into units and topics that include announcements, assignments, discussion threads, quizzes, tests, and more. In this research study was to develop the evaluation model through learning management integrating unified instructions of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC) was administered methodology that following is belows.

2.1 Research Aims

1. To investigate and analyze the composition of indicators to evaluate learning the evaluation model through learning management integrating unified instructions (LMIUI) of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC)
2. To establish and develop a evaluation model for evaluating through learning management integrating unified instructions (LMIUI) of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC).
3. To assess the EM model using the (LMIUI) process of learning management integration under the OBEC.
4. To evaluate guidelines to assess of the EM model with the (LMIUI) process under the OBEC

2.2 Research Limitations

Researcher team conducted the research methodology with the research and development (R & D), divided into four phases.

2.2.1 The First Phase: Component of Research Limitation

To examine and analysis of indicators evaluating learning management, integrated unified instructions of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC) with the scoping research limitation was folloed as:

A. Data Source Limitation

Using the source limitation in this phase included of the professional experts who were learning management integrating unified instructions of the Basic Educational Teachers under the OBEC

B. Content Limitation

The contents of this study were composed of the theoretical concepts and content, the documents and related research, framing ideas about assessment of learning, which

management integrating unified instructions of the Basic Educational Teachers under the OBEC.

C. Variable Limitation

Variable limitation included in the model to evaluate the indicator in evaluating learning management, integrated unified instructions of the Basic Educational Teachers under the OBEC.

2.2.2 The Second Phase: The Creating and Developing Evaluation Model (EM)

This phase was created and developed the EM model to assess learning management integrating unified instructions of the Basic Educational Teachers under the OBEC. The scope of the research was followed as:

A. Data Source Limitation

Data sources used in this research phase, researchers have defined the resources to create and develop a model for evaluating learning management integrating unified instructions which consisted of 9 symposium based experts with the connoisseurship of luminaries.

B. Content Limitation

The contents of this study were to evaluate the components of the EM model consisted of six principles and goals that aim to evaluate the process and method of evaluation, evaluation criteria, the adoption, and the results to determine the appropriateness and feasibility that followed in the first phase and brought to trial in a real situation.

C. Variable Limitation

Variables include the terms of experts' perceptions of the EM modeling form to their confirming the appropriateness and possibility components of quality indicators to evaluate learning management integration.

2.2.3 The Third Phase: To Trial the Evaluation Model

The section was to trial evaluation model of the LMIUI under the OBEC, the scope of the research study followed as:

A. Data Source Limitation

Using the data sources were selected the volunteer (Volunteer Sampling) amounted to two groups that composed of the recipient of the assessment, and the board of assessors. Administrations with the sample size of recipients were divided into two groups that consisted of 13 teachers in 13 schools in each group. The first group was trained for teaching with the EM model; the second group has never trained with the EM model for teaching of the (LMIUI) process. In terms of the evaluator team were estimated of 52 evaluators including with of 13 school administrators from 13 schools, 13 teachers from 13 schools, 13 teachers whose status as the first group, and 13 teachers whose status as the second group from 13 schools were selected.

B. Content Limitation

The contents of this study were the concurrent validity forms of evaluation. Testing the differences of scores between teachers' outcomes in two groups with the Mann-Whitney U test was compared. The results, the mean score in the first group were higher than the second group, significantly.

D. Variable Limitation

The variables included the term of the independent variables that included of teachers, curriculum integration, the EM model, and the LMIUI under the OBEC.

2.3.4 The Fourth Phase: Assessing the EM Model

The fourth assessing the EM model to evaluate of the LMIUI under the OBEC that foloowed as:

A. Data Source Limitation

Data sources were examined to trial the EM model that including 52 involving sample of school administrators, trained teachers, non-trained teachers, and teachers friends whose sample size of 13 personnel in 13 school of the LMIUI under the OBEC.

B. Content Limitation

The contents of this study were to determine the effectiveness of the EM model through the LMIUI under the OBEC with the integrity of the components of the EM model, the great feature of the assessment form, which compliance assessed of four aspects; such as; the utility for possibility, the feasibility of appropriate (propriety) and accuracy (Accuracy) by a panel of evaluators.

C. Variable Limitation

The variables included with the experts' perceptions in four aspects, namely; the Utility, the Feasibility, the Propriety, and Accuracy for the LMIUI under the OBEC of the EM model.

2.3 Research Procedures

To minister of the research procedure was divided into four stages that contained with the first phase was integated and analysis of indicators to assess learning for the LMIUI under the OBEC of the EM model for in order to assess the indicator component. The second phase was created and developed for the LMIUI under the OBEC of the EM model. The third phase was assessed the EM model through the for the LMIUI under the OBEC. The fourth phase was evaluated the EM model through the for the LMIUI under the OBEC. EM model through the LMIUI under the OBEC were associated.

2.4 Research Instruments

Characteristics of the research instruments included with the *Structured Interviews*, the *Appropriability and Feasibility Assessment*, and the *Recording Repertoire Model*.

A. The Structured Interviews (SI)

The Structured Interviews (SI) was qualified for interviewing the professional experts to obtain information about the EM model through the LMIUI under the OBEC on the learning management, the indicator learning management, and the criteria for evaluating learning management. The experts were to consider the consistency of content; the index was calculated in accordance IOC (Index of Item Objective Congruence) as its concept of Rovinelli and Hambleton (2015) has indicated that the consistency index of item as ranged from 0.60 to 1.00.

The Appropriability and Feasibility Assessment (AFA)

The Appropriability and Feasibility Assessment (AFA) was designed to evaluate on the draft format assessment of the indicators and evaluation criteria. It is a query the closed end of the five-level scale.

The Recording Repertoire Model (RRM)

The Recording Repertoire Model (RRM) was a comment section with the critiques of the experts on the composition of indicators and evaluation criteria. At the meeting, the symposium based experts (Connoisseurship) were recorded of the repertoire to comment section.

2.5 Sample

The sample size was selected with the volunteer sampling technique in two groups, which sample consisted of 13 trained teachers and 13 non trained teachers groups from 13 schools; experts' perceptions of 9 evaluators and recipients; the evaluator team consisted of 52 school directors, the academic teachers, teachers, and teacher colleagues who set of each team at 13 personnel from 13 schools; and the board of evaluators who were selected from the Roi-Et Primary Educational Service Area Office 1 under the OBEC.

2.6 Data analysis

The experts' perceptions were obtained using the Medium (Mdn), Interquartile Range (IQR), Percentage, Means, and Standard Deviation were analysed with the connoisseurships.

2.7 Data Collection

Data collections were composed with the professional expert interviews of the connoisseurship, administrative cooperation, explain and detail to the volunteer sampling group, and to lead letter inviting school administrators and the board of assessors for meeting were administered.

3. Results

The aims of research study were to develop the evaluation model (EM) through learning management integrating unified instructions (LMIUI) of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC) to administer into four phases; to investigate and analysis of indicators to assess learning, to create and develop a EM model for evaluating the LMIUI, to assess the EM model using the LMIUI, and to evaluate the EM model through form to assess learning integration services. The results of these research findings have found that:

The evaluation of the development the EM model through learning management integrating unified instructions (LMIUI) of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC) to assess of the learning Management integration services of teachers in schools should contain four components indicated that teachers' preparing to teach in sixth indicators, the learning process with ten indicators, the learning medias and innovations obtained of four indicators, and assessment and evaluation contained as ten indicators, respectively.

The Formats of the EM through the LMIUI for the Basic Educational teachers under the OBEC included of the rationale for the assessment, the goal of the evaluation, focused on the evaluation target (components and indicators). In terms of the evaluation process and method consisted of four steps: preparatory assessment, the evaluation process, the conclusion of the assessment, and reporting evaluation summary steps. The evaluation criteria was an absolute criteria by fixing a percentage.

The evaluating guidelines contained of the descriptions and application quality, and the evaluators. Statistically significant was evaluated of the evaluating instruments, data collection, data analysis, and the evaluation summary report are appropriate and the possibility is high level, evidently.

In terms of the quality of the EM through the LMIUI for the Basic Educational teachers under the OBEC, it has found that, the validity (Concurrent Validity) with the average mean scores of the trained teachers was higher than the non trained teachers groups and when comparisons between of two groups that were differentiated significantly at level of 0.01. The perceptions of the volunteer sampling groups were associated with the trial the EM model were commented that the components and indicators on overall and individual components also found at a high level, interestingly.

Focused on the implementations of learning process with the EM model through the LMIUI for the Basic Educational teachers under the OBEC on the possibility, appropriability, accuracy, and usefulness scales were reasonable at a high level all on four scales. The perceptions of involving groups who were the trial evaluators were guided that the developing the evaluation model through learning management

integrating unified instructions of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC) are provided and evidence of high level, responsibility.

4. Discussions

The researcher team was reported to the discussion frame for debate by presenting that following as: the results of the analysis and synthesis of the components of the EM model through the LMIUI for the Basic Educational teachers under the OBEC, the creating a guide for assessing and evaluating learning management integration, the results of the trial of the EM model, and the results of the evaluation formats of the EM model.

The evaluation of the development the EM model through learning management integrating unified instructions (LMIUI) of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC) to assess of the earning Management integration services of teachers in schools should contain four components indicated that teachers' preparing to teach in sixth indicators, the learning process with ten indicators, the learning medias and innovations obtained of four indicators, and assessment and evaluation contained as ten indicators, respectively that results are in line with the policy of the Ministry of Education in educational reform in the second decade (2552-2561 BE), the concept of education is important, a good teacher must have the ability to manage learning effectively requires working concept systems, which includes the processes and productivity. The clear frameworks for the integration of learning management are emphasized (Office of Basic Education. 2009: 5-6) and Kiddee (2004: 166-169) who reported that the indicators of teaching the learners were comprised of four major components, such as; learning environment, learning factor introduction, learning process, and learning productivity.

The Formats of the EM through the LMIUI for the Basic Educational teachers under the OBEC included of the rationale for the assessment, the goal of the evaluation, focused on the evaluation target (components and indicators). In terms of the evaluation process and method consisted of four steps: preparatory assessment, the evaluation process, the conclusion of the assessment, and reporting evaluation summary steps. The evaluation criteria was an absolute criteria by fixing a percentage. The evaluating guidelines contained of the descriptions and application quality, and the evaluators. Statistically significant was evaluated of the evaluating instruments, data collection, data analysis, and the evaluation summary report are appropriate and the possibility is high level. These components and indicators to evaluate the suitable comprehensive and possible adoption assessment, learning management in a real situation which in reality teachers who often do not have the opportunity to be

evaluated. There is no role or involvement in the indicator, not have enlist in the performance of their own. This responsibility for the indicator with the benchmarks' relationships to the teacher who often instruct a group of qualified professionals or academic supervisors. Mostly from higher education institutions, the lead indicators and quality criteria defined may not be consistent with the teacher practice (Vongvanij, 2001: 17), this research was designed to determine the suitability and feasibility of the components and indicators for evaluating learning management integrated unified states.

Requiring teachers to become specialists in the comments section for improving indicators and criteria to be appropriate and possible acceptance of the application in real life situations to determine the weight of the components in the assessment. Professional experts have to focus on the process of learning the most of the important weight of 35%, followed as the yield learning factors, the concept of learning, and the creation of partnership networks to learn. The weight of equal importance, 30%, 20%, 10% and 5%, respectively, indicating the views of experts, which is the study of measurement and evaluation and the learning management integration services to consider that the learning process is paramount. Reflect that teachers are individuals who play a role in learning according to Horwitz and et., al (2009: 1) that the success of the students in the class. The strategy relies on education of teachers that the policy and promotion continued according to the Office of the Basic Education (2011: 5) that the education of the country that aim to excellence in management education in Thailand to develop the quality required to compete with other countries. The teacher is the most important factor, teachers must have the ability to manage the course. How can development activities?, as well as materials used in teaching to achieve the standard of teaching and learning of students' knowledge can continue to learn effectively.

In terms of the quality of the EM through the LMIUI for the Basic Educational teachers under the OBEC, it has found that, the validity (Concurrent Validity) with the average mean scores of the trained teachers was higher than the non-trained teachers groups and when comparisons between of two groups that were differentiated significantly at level of 0.01. The perceptions of the volunteer sampling groups were associated with the trial the EM model were commented that the components and indicators on overall and individual components also found at a high level, interestingly.

In terms of the quality of the trial of the EM through the LMIUI for the Basic Educational teachers under the OBEC, it has found that, the validity (Concurrent Validity) with the average mean scores of the trained teachers was higher than the non-trained teachers groups and when comparisons between of two groups that were differentiated significantly at level of 0.01. The perceptions of the volunteer sampling groups were associated with the trial the EM model were commented that the

components and indicators on overall and individual components also found at a high level, interestingly. These found that this form of assessment was developed to provide results that correspond to the reality. The group can't be appearance of validity (Concurrent Validity). The validity of this condition is to examine the construct validity (Construct Validity), sometimes called the theory signify the educational tools that can be measured or storage characteristics (Buason, 2008: 128-129), reported that the evaluation model through learning management integrating unified instructions of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC) was developed a direct or efficient implementation. This development has created a very powerful concept to support the theory. Using a variety of techniques and passed the quality check by expert groups. They were assessed with reasonable accuracy; coverage is acceptable that can be used to assess learning integration services of the LMIUI, correctly.

The implementations of learning process with the EM model through the LMIUI for the Basic Educational teachers under the OBEC on the possibility, appropriability, accuracy, and usefulness scales were reasonable at a high level all on four scales. The perceptions of involving groups who were the trial evaluators were guided that the developing the evaluation model through learning management integrating unified instructions of the Basic Educational Teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC) are provided and evidence of high level, responsibility. This is because the researcher team was conducted to provide stakeholders with an understanding of the principles and details about the correct valuation model. That assessment to improve the quality of learning management integrated unified for the Basic Educational teachers under the OBEC with the critical evaluation model that it was developed by the researchers has created an efficient manner. Through the review process to determine the suitability of an expert in cognitive assessment and learning management solutions of teachers in the basic education. The rate used for each element by weight, the importance of each element varies accordingly. As well as methods and tools to collect the appropriate information on each element. The evaluation criteria are appropriate admittedly cause reliability to evaluate addition to developing models to assess the time the research was conducted by the research and development process. This was the method used in the research process and ensure the quality of products to ensure that the product was created to put into practical purposes (Buason, 2009: 94), so the development of an evaluation model to assess learning integration services through learning management integrating unified instructions of the Basic Educational teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC) with the research and development process, it was formed to evaluate on the possibility, appropriability, accuracy, and usefulness scales to be recognized, relevantly.

5. Suggestions

1. Implementation of teacher evaluation is feeling fine. Therefore, the researcher should consult the manual thoroughly assessed, understanding evaluation guide synchronization that should be followed as the procedures specified in the manual seriously throughout the reviews. The assessment results are accepted by all parties, which can be used for evaluation and professional development for teachers to effectively further.
2. Using the leadership evaluation model to evaluate the students in basic education to be effective should have the skills to assess students before proceeding to assess the real situation.
3. Teachers should be evaluated for use in their own development. The details of the assessment, the elements and indicator below the threshold with a low rating. The analysis of the causes and solutions to improve the development and learning management integrating unified instructions integrating unified instructions that it is reflected more quality, increasingly.
4. The agency responsible for learning management, integrated unified instructions of the Basic Educational teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC). There should be an assessment of the implementation of the model. The results were analyzed of the strategy development and training to fulfill the potential of teachers to become teachers in the future.
5. The important evaluation conditions to use the model to evaluate the efficiency and effectiveness should have: school administrators must have a clear policy on the use of assessment tools in development, learning management, integrated unified instructions of the Basic Educational teachers under Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC). This means the assessment is not hidden agenda, as a result of living conditions for the feat is promoted, etc. The feat should be promoted as having no political assessment (Politics of Evaluation) or to create a good image for its units. Evaluation is a tool that can be used in the administration did not actually see the results of the assessment goals. Assessment is an assessment needs to be a good friend with a great desire for each other, a mutual acceptance, the goal or realize mutual benefits.

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